

A Hybrid Anti-Islanding Protection Scheme for VSM Based DG Inverter

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Abstract:

This paper proposes a new hybrid AIP system for VSM inverters that can be used to integrate DG sources into the grid. Because the proposed system can be integrated into the control of DG inverters without requiring any further hardware or controller changes. The voltage and frequency support capabilities of virtual synchronous machine (VSM) technology make it an appealing control technique for inverter-based distributed generation (DG). It is necessary for DG inverters to have an anti-islanding protection (AIP) system with high precision because of the safety concerns of workers and hazardous operations, AIP approach has a significant advantage. As a result, the AIP scheme's performance has been verified by a series of simulated tests.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Due to rising global temperatures, interest in DG technologies including as photovoltaic (PV) systems and wind turbines has skyrocketed in recent decades. Distributed generators have risen in popularity during the last decade, and certain utilities have achieved very high penetration levels. Despite this, the dispute over many technological issues continues to flare between public utilities and private producers. Anti-islanding protection is

perhaps the most disputed, with the most conservative and modern ways each relying on a dependable high-speed communication-based transfer-trip scheme and a local passive approach method that merely depends on measurements of the voltage waveform.

The DG interconnection standards specify that all distributed generation (DG) installations must comply with the anti-islanding and line protection criteria. All defects on the feeder to which the DG is attached must be detected, whereas faults on a nearby feeder must not be disconnected. Relays are usually sufficient for this purpose however, power electronic generators may necessitate additional solutions due to their limited contribution toward short circuits. The concept of anti-islanding has been the focus of several investigations. In order to distinguish between islanding and grid-connected operation, passive approaches use local measurements of voltage and current, along with variables derived from these values, while active approaches use voltage or frequency perturbation by the DG, an approach intended to be benign while the grid is present but to destabilize the system when the substrate is present. It has been claimed that thyristor-based devices can be used to identify faults in the grid. As in the case of

"active islanding," this approach could be condemned solely for its influence on power quality. Nuisance tripping is a problem with very long or noisy grids or feeders. The concept of anti-islanding has been the focus of several investigations. In order to distinguish between islanding and grid-connected operation, passive approaches use local measurements of voltage and current, along with variables derived from these values, while active approaches use voltage or frequency perturbation by the DG, an approach intended to be benign while the grid is present but to destabilize the system when the substrate is present. It has been claimed that thyristor-based devices can be used to identify faults in the grid. As in the case of "active islanding," this approach could be condemned solely for its influence on power quality. Nuisance tripping is a problem with very long or noisy grids or feeders. New hybrid AIP schemes for inverters in the DG are the major contribution of this paper. For the existing solutions [1– [12]], this AIP method has the following advantages:

- Because it doesn't require any additional sensors or power devices to be installed in DG inverters.
- Active and passive AIP methods are combined in the AIP scheme, which does not require a communication network. Therefore, there is no possibility of triggering instability or power quality issues because the sophisticated disturbance injection approach has been avoided.
- The AIP scheme also eliminates malfunctioning when local loads are equivalent to the DG inverter's power supply.

System metrics like as active power, reactive power, and voltage magnitude mismatches are used by the AIP technique to detect an islanding condition. When an islanding condition is detected, the AIP system removes the inverter from the main grid and prevents it from re-connecting. Analytical modeling of the proposed AIP scheme is described in a thorough operating concept. Time-domain simulations are presented to verify the proposed AIP scheme's performance in several various circumstances, such as adjusting the inverter's reference power, adding a high load, and generating grid faults. During the last decade, several concepts for VSMs have been presented with different names and different practical implementations [14,15 -19]. The first review studies providing an overview of implementations have been recently published in [17,20], with an attempt to define a classification framework presented in [17]. The review in [17] also highlights how some implementations offer only partially the benefits of the SMs while only a few can ensure features as island operation of single or multiple units. Most previous studies of VSM-based control strategies have presented implementation schemes which have been verified by time-domain simulations and/or laboratory experiments. A first study that included detailed modeling and small-signal stability of a VSM implementation was presented in [21]. However, this model was

mainly developed for tuning of the converter control loop and did not consider the primary power-frequency control, or the dynamics of the grid frequency detection needed to ensure implementation of the VSM damping effect that adapts to variations in the grid frequency. A VSM system model addressing also these issues was recently presented in [22]. Anti-islanding protection is required of any distributed generator connecting to the Distribution network, to protect against the case that DG continues to energize the feeder when the utility has opened-creating an unintentional island. An unintentional island, although rather unlikely in real life, could be created by one of two scenarios.

II. OPERATION PRINCIPLE OF THE PROPOSED ANTI-ISLANDING PROTECTION SCHEME:

It is possible to implement the proposed AIP method using a variety of DG inverter controllers. VSM controllers for the DG inverter are an intriguing alternative. In this study, an example implementation of the AIP scheme using the VSM controller is presented. When using a phase-locked-loop controller, the VSM controller can operate in either a revolving or stationary frame, such as a synchronverter [23-24], robust droop controller technique that does not necessitate the use of a PLL. An overview of a VSM DG inverter and controller may be found in Figure 1. The inverter sends active and reactive power to the grid according to its specified power and frequency. The inverter's output power can be supplied by other devices. The inverter sends the active power, and the reactive power, to

the grid according to its set power and. The power sent by the inverter can be given by

$$P = P_{set} = \frac{V_o^2}{R_T} \text{--- (1)}$$

$$Q = Q_{set} = V_o^2 \left(\frac{1}{2\pi f L_T} - 2\pi f C_T \right) \text{--- (2)}$$

where V_o is the capacitor voltage magnitude, f is the grid frequency and R_T, L_T, C_T are the equivalent resistance, inductance and capacitance seen by the DG inverter as shown in Fig. 1. If multiple DG sources are connected at the PCC, (1) and (2) are still valid and each of DG sources will have their equivalent, R_T, L_T and C_T .

Fig. 1 VSM-based DG inverter and its controller.

The grid controls voltage and frequency in the grid-connected mode. The role of the DG sources in system regulation is minimal. Voltage and frequency regulation cannot be achieved if the DG inverters are operating in continuous power mode. Because of this, DG inverters contribute to voltage and frequency on an island in an island operation. It is because the generation of both active and reactive power is controlled that voltage and frequency are maintained. The grid impedance

variation can be used to detect an islanding condition and notice it quickly. [25].

$$\Delta P = \frac{2V_o}{R_T} \Delta V_o - \frac{V_o^2}{R_T^2} \Delta R_T \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta Q = 2V_o \left(\frac{1}{2\pi f L_T} - 2\pi f C_T \right) \Delta V_o - \frac{V_o^2}{2\pi f L_T^2} \Delta L_T - 2\pi f V_o^2 \Delta C_T - V_o^2 \left(\frac{1}{2\pi f^2 L_T} + 2\pi f C_T \right) \Delta f \quad (4)$$

When the inverter is linked to the grid, it typically runs at or near unity power factor, with reactive power Q_{set} set to zero. When a power outage occurs on an island, the inverter can either supply or absorb reactive power depending on the associated load, L_T and C_T . Adsorption or generation of reactive power is done by inverters for voltage or frequency stability. As a result, the reactive power delivered by an inverter in an islanding condition is likely to differ from the reference reactive power Q_{set} . The difference in reactive power is the first criterion for determining an islanding state. It is the DG inverter that regulates voltage and frequency during island operations. At least a threshold limit Q_L of 0.1pu is met when reactive power mismatch Q surpasses the threshold limit Q_L .

$$|\Delta Q| \geq Q_L \quad (5)$$

If the inverter output current reaches its limit, it can no longer increase its power to maintain the voltage magnitude.

Fig.2 Control block diagram of the proposed AIP scheme.

In an island operation, the DG inverter provides or absorbs power to maintain voltage and frequency. Inverters can only boost their output current to a certain point before they can no longer maintain the same voltage. In this case, the voltage magnitude will tend to exceed from its operating range 0.95 -1.05 pu. The voltage mismatch defined by

$$\Delta V = E^* - V_o \quad (6)$$

Where E^* is the rated voltage, may exceed from the standard operating range. In severe cases, a voltage instability/collapse may occur. Hence, in addition to the power mismatch, the voltage mismatch has been considered as another condition for the AIP scheme if exceeds the threshold limit, V_L . i.e., (6) is satisfied.

$$|\Delta V| \geq V_L \quad (7)$$

The proposed AIP scheme is depicted by a logic diagram in Fig. 2.

The logic in the AIP scheme is set such a way that if in addition to the condition in (5), at least one of the conditions from (6) and (7) are satisfied, the AIP scheme assumes the situation as an islanding condition.

The working procedure of the AIP scheme can be summarized in the following.

- The reactive power mismatch exceeds the threshold limit Q_L for a delay time T_D is satisfied. The delay time should be set according to the standard grid code requirement. To comply with the IEEE 1547 Standard, the delay time should be set less than 2 s [26].
- If the reactive power mismatch does not exceed the threshold limit Q_L for the duration of the delay time T_D but the active power mismatch exceeds the threshold limits, P_L for the duration of the delay time T_D , the AIP will send a command signal to change Q_{set} and then recalculate the ΔQ . If the new power mismatch exceeds limit Q_L , then AIP scheme recognizes the situation as an islanding condition, however active power and/or voltage magnitude mismatch exceed their threshold limits P_L and V_L , then AIP scheme recognizes the situation as an islanding condition/ and the islanding detection.

Boost Circuit and Its Control:

For two-stage PV generation system, boost chopper circuit is always used as the DC/DC converter. Since the output voltage of PV cell is low, the use of boost circuit will enable low-voltage PV array to be used, as a result, the total cost will be reduced. A capacitor is generally connected between PV array and the boost circuit, which is used to reduce high frequency harmonics. Figure 3(a) is the configuration of the boost circuit and its control system.

Fig. 3 (a) Boost circuit of PV system.

Fig.3 (b) shows the Battery energy storage system (BESS). Battery energy storage system (BESS) is composed of a battery bank, a bi-directional DC/DC converter and control system. The system should be able to operating in two directions: the battery can be charged to store the extra energy and also can discharge the energy to loads. The utility grid is considered as a backup source and the battery bank serves as a short- duration power source to meet the load demands which cannot be fully met by the PV system, particularly during fluctuations of the solar or transient periods.

Fig. 3 (b) BESS for PV array.

The primary objective of the battery converter is to maintain the common dc link

- Fuzzification using continuous universe of discourse.
- Implication using Mamdani's min operator. Defuzzification using the height method.

Fuzzification:

Membership function values are assigned to the linguistic variables, using seven fuzzy subsets: NB (Negative Big), NM (Negative Medium), NS (Negative Small), ZE (Zero), PS (Positive Small), PM (Positive Medium), and PB (Positive Big). The partition of fuzzy subsets and the shape of membership $CE(k)$ $E(k)$ function adapt the shape up to appropriate system. The value of input error and change in error are normalized by an input scaling factor

ΔE	NB	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PB
NB	NB	NB	NB	NB	NM	NS	Z
NM	NB	NB	NB	NM	NS	Z	PS
NS	NB	NB	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM
Z	NB	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PB
PS	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PB	PB
PM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PB	PB	PB
PB	Z	PS	PM	PB	PB	PB	PB

Fig. 5 MEMBERSHIP FUNCTIONS

In this system the input scaling factor has been designed such that input values are between -1 and +1. The triangular shape of the membership function of this arrangement presumes that for any particular $E(k)$ input there is only one dominant fuzzy subset.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS:

Using PI controller:

(a) V_o (b) I_o (c) freq (d) Active power (W) (e) Reactive power (kvar)

(i)

(a) V_o (b) I_o (c) freq (d) Active power (W) (e) Reactive power (kvar)

(ii)

(a) Vo (b)Io (c) freq (d) Active power (W) (e) Reactive power (kvar)
(iii)

Fig 6.1 :i,ii,iii: Performance of the AIP scheme: (a) Change of the Power Reference, (b) a load connection and disconnection and (c) a fault in the grid. The IDS is zero for these cases and no false signal is generated by the AIP scheme.

(a)

(b)

Fig 6.2 Performance of the AIP scheme: Islanding occurs when (a) the local load is smaller than Pset Pset = 15 kW and Pload = 5 kW and (b) the local load is equal to Pset .Pset = Pload = 15 kW. The IDS becomes 1 for these cases and an islanding condition is detected.

From fig 6.2, the IDS become 1 at 3.25 s. The islanding condition is detected after 0.75 s of actual islanding occurred which is the specified time, 0.75 s set by the AIP designer. The system is designed such a way that when the IDS becomes 1, then CB 2 is opened to isolate the inverter from the rest of the grid. As can be seen, the current to the grid i_g becomes zero at 3.25 s since CB 2 is opened. After isolation at 3.25 s, the inverter operates in the stand-alone mode and supplies power to the local load. Fig. 6.2 (b). P_{set} and Q_{set} are 15 kW and 3 kVar. The local load is equal to P_{set} . In order to comply with IEEE 1547 Standard [7], in addition to a resistive load, the load network contains a 15-kVar capacitive and a 15-kVar inductive elements that cancel each other out. This creates a self-resonating island. Initially, the system is operating in the grid- connected mode, there is no violation of the threshold limit until 2.5 s. At 2.5 s, an islanding condition occurs. The reactive power

mismatch $|Q|$ has exceeded the threshold limit QL when the active power mismatch $|P|$ and the voltage mismatch $|V|$ do not exceed the threshold limits PL and VL since $P_{set} = P_{load}$ and the inverter regulates the voltage. During the time from 2.5 s to 3.25 s, only the reactive power mismatch exceeds the limit Q_L . Since no violation occurs except the reactive power mismatch for 0.75 s duration, the AIP generates a command signal to change P_{set} for a step of $P_{set} = 0.125$ pu at 3.25 s. For this change of P_{set} , the active power mismatch $|P|$ exceeds the threshold limit P_L . Thus, (10), and (11) are satisfied. The IDS becomes 1 as shown in the bottom plot of Fig. 6.2(b). The islanding condition is detected. Hence, CB 2 operates to isolate the inverter from the rest of the grid. After isolation, the inverter operates in the islanding-mode and supplies stable power to the local load. The proposed AIP scheme works properly and can successfully detect the islanding condition.

Using Fuzzy controller:

(a) Vo (b)Io (c) freq (d) Active power (W) (e) Reactive power (kvar)

(i)

(a) Vo (b)Io (c) freq (d) Active power (W) (e) Reactive power (kvar)

(ii)

(a) Vo (b)Io (c) freq (d) Active power (W) (e) Reactive power (kvar)

(iii)

Fig 6.3 represents: Performance of the AIP scheme: (a) Change of the Power Reference, (b) a load connection and disconnection and (c) a fault in the grid. The IDS is zero for these cases and no false signal is generated by the AIP scheme.

(a)

(b)

6.4 Performance of the AIP scheme: Islanding occurs when (a) the local load is smaller than P_{set} .

$P_{set} = 15$ kW and $P_{load} = 5$ kW and (b) the local load is equal to P_{set} . $P_{set} = P_{load} = 15$ kW. The IDS becomes 1 for these cases and an islanding condition is detected.

An initial simulation was run with P_{set} and Q_{set} modified by a command signal. Islanding is not a condition that may be initiated. In Fig.6.1, we see the time-domain reactions (i). Simulated load connections and disconnections were used to test the AIP scheme's performance. For this simulation, we employed a 20-kW local load and shifted it. Figure 6.1 (ii) shows the simulation results for the case where 20 kW is connected to the grid for 2.5 s and disconnected for 4 s. Due to its dynamic droop setting, the inverter is currently helping the grid. There is still no islanding condition because the IDS is 0. There are three phases involved in this simulation, which may be shown in Figure 6.1(iii). There have been five cycles of clearing the problem following its inception at 2.5 s. Overcoming imbalances in power and voltage is possible even if the problem has been cleared. The IDS has

CONCLUSION:

A unique hybrid AIP method for DG inverters is presented in this research. The signal obtained from the DG inverter controller is detected no islanding situations. As a result, in the event of a grid failure, the AIP system will not generate a misleading signal. An islanding-mode inverter is activated after isolation and offers steady power to a local load. In order to detect the islanding condition, the proposed AIP technique is effective. Better rise time and active power to 16KW, and improved reactive power to 4kvar can be shown in fig 6.3 from fig 6.4 utilising a fuzzy controller. Improved power quality and fault clearing time are achieved by utilising a fuzzy controller at the 2.5sec rise time, where active power is increased to 16KW, and reactive power is

increased to 4 kvar, and peak overshoot is decreased. At 3.3 sec settling time is improved such that power quality is improved. There are no false IDS created as a result of the AIP method, and overall system performance is good. used to implement the AIP system. The key benefit of this suggested AIP scheme is that it can be integrated into the control of inverters without requiring any additional hardware or changes to the controller. The suggested AIP technique is based on local measurements and does not rely on the communication network. It identifies islanding by continuously monitoring active power, reactive power, and voltage magnitude mismatch, which has been proved to be a viable alternative to the impedance variation measurement technique. The difficult disturbance injection approach in the active method has been avoided, removing the possibility of triggering instability and power quality concerns, as well as the failure of passive methods when the local load is equivalent to the power supplied by the inverter. The AIP method is put to the test in every imaginable islanding scenario. The suggested AIP scheme's islanding detection function has been confirmed by simulation results.

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